

Synthesis, Spectra and Physiological Activity of 7H-Pyrano (3,2-e) Benzoxazole-7-Ones

Y. D. REDDY and V. V. SOMAYAJULU

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Warangal-506 004

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A few 2-aryl and 2-heterocyclic substituted (3,2-e) benzoxazoles have been synthesised by condensing 5-amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with aromatic and heterocyclic carboxylic acids employing polyphosphoric acid as cyclodehydrating agent. The ultraviolet, infrared, nmr and mass spectra of these compounds have been presented. A study of antibacterial and antifungal activities of these compounds has revealed that 2-(3-pyridyl), 2-(4-pyridyl) and 2-*p*-chlorophenyl pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-ones possess high antifungal activity at 100 ppm dilution.

A wide range of physiological properties are found to be associated with coumarin and its derivatives.

Among the antibiotics, belonging to the coumarin series, Novobiocin and Coumermycin A₁ and A₂ are the outstanding ones. Interest in the oxazolo-pyran group of heterocycles was stimulated by the isolation of an oxazolo (3,4-d) coumarin from the broad spectrum antibiotic Novobiocin¹. The synthesis of a number of oxazolo α -pyrones, γ -pyrones and their benzo derivatives followed, as analogues of this antibiotic, for evaluating their physiological properties²⁻⁵. Moreover, a number of oxazolo (3,4)⁶, (6,7) and (7,8)⁷ coumarins have earlier been made and were found to exhibit appreciable antibacterial activity.

The survey of literature on pyrano benzoxazoles revealed that with the exception of a single coumarino (5,6-d) oxazole obtained accidentally during an attempted Claisen migration⁸ no oxazole system has so far been built on the 5,6-positions of the coumarin moiety. Hence it has been considered worthwhile to synthesize a few 7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-ones, more simply termed as [coumarino (5,6)-oxazoles] for the purpose of physiological evaluation.

For the purpose of synthesising the title compounds, 5-amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (I) was taken as the starting material, which could be prepared as outlined below. Hydroquinone has been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate to give 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin by an improved method⁹. This was nitrated with a mixture of 70% nitric acid and concentrated sulphuric acid under the conditions reported earlier¹⁰ to get 6-hydroxy-5-nitro-4-methylcoumarin. Reduction¹⁰ of the latter by treatment with dithionite gave 5-amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin. In our earlier communication¹¹ polyphosphoric acid has been used as a cyclodehydrating agent for the preparation of oxazoles. Encouraged by the results and yields, it was extended to the synthesis of 7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-ones (II) (Chart I) using easily accessible aromatic and heterocyclic carboxylic

acids. The present work describes the results of these investigations.

In the present investigation the acids utilised for condensation include benzoic acid, and its *o*-chloro, *p*-chloro analogues, *o*- and *p*-toluic acids, 1- and 2-naphthoic acids, phenyl acetic acid, and pyridine-3- and 4-carboxylic acids. The yields have been nearly quantitative except with pyridine-3- and 4-carboxylic acids.

In general the reaction mixture was heated first at 150-60° for 1½ hrs and then at 200-205° for a further period of 3 hrs. The resulting 7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-ones have been included in Table 3.

With a view to confirm the structure of these compounds a few members of this series have been prepared as typical examples by alternate method, viz. condensing *o*-amino hydroxycoumarins with appropriate aldehyde in nitrobenzene medium as communicated earlier¹². It may be pointed out that the yields of the desired oxazoles by the latter method are relatively lower than those obtained by the polyphosphoric acid method.

Refluxing 5-amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (I) with acetic anhydride directly yielded 2-methyl-7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-one, thus constituting a one step method in comparison with the work of Ellis *et al*¹³ who reported O-N diacetate under similar conditions which was pyrolysed to get cyclic product.

TABLE-1

Compound	Assignment			
	9Me	8C-H	4C-H and 5C-H AB-system	Substituent at 2-phenyl or benzyl
(a) 2- <i>p</i> -Toluyyl-7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7- one.	δ 2.95 (d, J = 1 Hz)	δ 6.30 (q, J = 1 Hz)	δ 7.15-7.3 (J = 9 Hz) δ 7.55-7.70 (J = 9 Hz) δ A = 459.6 Hz δ B = 438.4 Hz	δ 8.05-8.20 (d, J = 9 Hz 2', 6' C-H) δ 2.50 (s, Me) δ 7.30-7.50 (d, J = 9 Hz 3', 5' C-H)
(b) 2- <i>o</i> -Toluyyl-7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7- one	δ 2.85 (d, J = 1 Hz)	δ 6.30 (q, J = 1 Hz)	δ 7.15-7.3 (J = 9 Hz) δ 7.6-7.75 (J = 9 Hz) δ A = 459.6 Hz δ B = 438.4 Hz	δ 8.05-8.25 (m, 2' C-H) δ 2.75 (s, Me) δ 7.30-7.55 (m, 3', 4', 5' C-H)
(c) 2-Benzyl-7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7- one	δ 2.85 (d, J = 2 Hz)	δ 6.28 (q, J = 2 Hz)	δ 7.10-7.26 (J = 10 Hz) δ 7.44-7.6 (J = 10 Hz) δ A = 454.6 Hz δ B = 433.4 Hz	δ 7.28-7.40 (m, Ar C-H) δ 4.33 (s, Methylene)

Spectral characteristics of pyrano (3, 2-e) benzoxazoles :

Ultraviolet spectra : Four broad regions of absorption have been noticed with all the pyrano (3, 2-e) benzoxazoles, at 315 ± 2 nm, 304 ± 1 nm, 290 ± 5 nm and 245 ± 5 nm. The first two bands are assignable to the cinnamoyl chromophore (a) and the effect of the β -methyl substituent (b) results in a splitting of this chromophore into the observed two maxima.

The maxima at 290 ± 5 nm and 245 ± 5 nm must be due to the 2-aryl benzoxazole moiety which is analogous to the 2-phenyl benzoxazole bands recorded earlier around the same region¹⁴. In the case of the 2-(1-naphthyl) and 2-(2-naphthyl) analogues, additional bands were recorded at 255 nm, 275 nm and 360 ± 5 nm for the naphthalene ring transitions. With the 2-(3-pyridyl) and 2-(4-pyridyl) derivatives, the band due to the pyridine system seems to have merged with the 304 ± 1 nm band, as evidenced by the increase in intensity for this band in these compounds.

Infrared spectra : A strong band around $1735-1710$ cm^{-1} confirmed the coumarin carbonyl. Bands around 1570 cm^{-1} , 1350 cm^{-1} , 1050 cm^{-1} are characteristic of oxazole ring system.

Nmr spectra : The nmr spectra of pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazoles have been recorded on a Varian A-60 NMR spectrometer in deuterated chloroform. The results have been included in Table 1.

The most important feature from the structural point of view is the appearance of the 4,5-protons of the coumarin moiety at δ 7.15 to δ 7.38 and δ 7.55 to δ 7.78 as doublets with a coupling constant of 8-10 CPS, which confirms the angular nature of these compounds.

Mass spectra : The mass spectra were recorded on a R.M.U.-6L Mass spectrometer with inlet

temperature ranging from $150-200^\circ$ and an electron beam energy of 70 ev.

The mass spectra of four pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazoles have been recorded. The molecular ions (a) have been recorded as the base peaks in the case of 2-(*o*-chlorophenyl) and 2-(2-naphthyl) analogues, while with 1-(*o*-toluyyl) and 2-(3-pyridyl) compounds the molecular ion abundances are 85% and 94% respectively of the base peaks. Thus, these figures reflect the high stability of this system to electron impact.

The major fragmentation mode is the loss of carbon monoxide, as observed in the case of simple coumarins¹⁵. This is followed by the loss of hydrogen radical from (b) with simultaneous ring expansion yielding highly abundant ion (c).

The ion (c) has been found to be the base peak with the 2-(3-pyridyl) derivative, while (b) formed the base peak in the case of the 2-*o*-toluyyl analogue. Other ions prominent in the spectra, except with the 2-(3-pyridyl) derivative, are the RCN^+ ions obtained by the cleavage of the oxazole ring. A comparison of the abundances of the M-CO and the RCN^+ fragments reveals that the α -pyrone is less stable to electron impact than the oxazole moiety. 2-(2-Naphthyl) derivative also gives an ion representing loss of H from C.

Physiological activity : All the above compounds have been tested for antibacterial activity using *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as representative species, employing the

TABLE—3

Sl. No.	Pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole	m.p. °C	% Yield	Calculated			Found			Solvent
				C	H	N	C	H	N	
(1)	2-Phenyl	211-12	76	73.6	4.0	5.1	73.3	4.1	5.2	Benzene
(2)	2-o-Chlorophenyl	197-98	92	65.5	3.2	4.5	65.3	3.3	4.7	Benzene-Pet. ether
(3)	2-p-Chlorophenyl	258-59	85	65.5	3.2	4.5	65.4	3.1	4.6	Benzene
(4)	2-o-Toluyyl	205	86	74.2	4.5	4.8	74.4	4.6	4.9	Benzene
(5)	2-p-Toluyyl	232-33	86	74.2	4.5	4.8	74.3	4.7	4.9	Benzene
(6)	2-(1-Naphthyl)	222-23	88	77.1	4.0	4.3	77.0	4.1	4.3	Benzene
(7)	2-(2-Naphthyl)	274-75	88	77.1	4.0	4.3	77.2	4.0	4.4	Benzene
(8)	2-Benzyl	164-65	90	74.2	4.5	4.8	74.3	4.6	4.9	Benzene-Pet. ether
(9)	2-(3-Pyridyl)	257-58	44	69.1	3.6	10.1	69.3	3.7	10.3	Benzene-Pet. ether
(10)	2-(4-Pyridyl)	260	45	69.1	3.6	10.1	69.2	3.6	10.3	Benzene
(11)	2-Methyl	165-66	80	67.0	4.7	6.5	67.3	4.6	6.3	Benzene

tube dilution method. None of the compounds are found to be antibacterial. The fungistatic activity has been assessed by the reduction in growth rate method¹⁶ employing *Aspergillus niger* (A.N.) and *Trichophyton semii* (T.S.) as the test organisms. The results of the bacteriostatic activity experiments have been included in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FUNGISTATIC ACTIVITY OF 7H-PYRANO (3, 2-e) BENZOXAZOLE-7-ONES

Sl. No.	Pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-one	Dilution : 100 p.p.m.	
		A. N. % Inhibition	T S. % Inhibition
(1)	2-Phenyl	60	60
(2)	2-o-Chlorophenyl	60	60
(3)	2-p-Chlorophenyl	80	80
(4)	2-o-Toluyyl	60	60
(5)	2-p-Toluyyl	20	20
(6)	2-(1-Naphthyl)	0	0
(7)	2-(2-Naphthyl)	20	20
(8)	2-Benzyl	60	60
(9)	2-(3-Pyridyl)	80	80
(10)	2-(4-Pyridyl)	80	80
(11)	2-Methyl	60	60

Experimental

Preparation of 7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-ones : (PPA method) : Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by stirring a mixture of phosphorous pentoxide (15 g) and ortho phosphoric acid (10 ml) at 100° for 1 hr. Then a mixture of 5-amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (0.005 mole) and appropriate acid (0.005 mole) was dropped into the above. This was heated with stirring first at 150-60° for 1½ hrs and then at 200-205° for a further period of 3 hrs. The reaction product was poured over ice cold water and the resulting solid was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. Recrystallisation was effected with appropriate solvent as indicated in Table 3.

Preparation of 7H-pyrano (3,2-e) benzoxazole-7-ones :

Nitrobenzene method : 5-Amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2 g), and aromatic aldehyde (2.5 g) viz. benzaldehyde and p-chlorobenzaldehyde

were refluxed for 4½ hrs. Nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation. The residue that was left in the flask was filtered, washed with petroleum ether to remove traces of nitrobenzene. Recrystallisation was effected from benzenepetroleum ether mixture to yield the corresponding oxazole.

Preparation of 2-methyl-7H-pyrano (3, 2-e) benzoxazole-7-one : 5-Amino-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.9 g) and acetic anhydride (15 ml) were refluxed for 1 hr and poured over crushed ice. The solid was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. The product on recrystallisation from benzene gave light violet crystals.

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